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Major immune receptors of the placenta.

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We measured total gene expression in the human placenta to understand immune receptor composition during human development *in utero*. The placenta was CD34+ and expressed Ly6E, Hcg18 and HLA-DQA1. Lyar and Lym4 were the other major placenta-enriched Ly antigens. Immune receptor composition in the human placenta was diverse and included Prt1 and Prt15, as well as Prss22, Lrrn3, Vstm4, and Ildr1. Fc receptors were expressed in the placenta including Fcgr1b and Fcgr2b. The placenta was Plac9+ and expressed Hcg18, Ifi44 and Ifit1b, and E-selectin. We defined here basic immunologic cell surface composition of the human placenta.

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